

Moisture Absorption Effects on Delamination Fracture Mechanisms of Carbon Fiber Polymeric Matrix Composites

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Abstract

The core emphasis of this study is the assessment of moisture effects on fracture processes and on delamination fracture toughness of two continuous fiber reinforced polymeric matrix composite laminates, graphite/epoxy and graphite/thermoplastics. The saturation level, maximum solubility, of sorbed moisture was significantly higher for thermoset resin matrix composites than for thermoplastic resin matrix composites. Delamination fracture toughness and fracture energy results were determined for thermoset and thermoplastic graphite fiber reinforced laminates. Whereas a reduction of fracture toughness was exhibited for thermoset composites due to matrix moisture absorption, essentially, no effect of moisture sorption was observed for delamination fracture toughness of thermoplastic composites. The reduction in the fracture toughness was due to degradation in crack tip craze and interfacial strength, and to the extent of moisture-induced plasticization of the epoxy matrix.

Keywords: delamination, graphite epoxy, graphite thermoplastic, laminate, moisture effects, fracture energy, fracture toughness, mode I, delamination fracture, plasticization

1.0 Introduction

The application of polymeric matrix composite (PMC) materials has proliferated in recent decades. Resin matrix composite materials have been widely used in structural applications in space and aerospace industries. Improvements in processing and manufacturing methods have led to affordability, and, consequently, spurred growth of composites in alternative applications, such as in marine environments. Many industries have embraced PMCs because of highly desirable specific strength and specific stiffness properties. Because of high specific stiffness and specific strength, lightweight composite structures can be tailored with static properties comparable to their monolithic structural materials counterpart. However, unlike most homogeneous, monolithic materials, composite laminae properties can be highly anisotropic. Often, anisotropic characteristics are used advantageously to configure composite laminates with highly directional properties and to fabricate dimensionally stable laminates that are functional over a wide temperature range [1].

It has been recognized for quite sometime that the static mechanical properties of PMCs are affected by various environments [2-7]. Of particular interest is the influence of humid environment (moisture) on mechanical properties, particularly, transverse static properties, and fracture behavior that is dominated by the matrix and interfacial properties. Depending on matrix phase chemistry, other fluids that are absorbed by the bulk matrix and by the interface phase can induce degradation. For most thermoset (epoxy) composites, the absorption of moisture modifies the strength, stiffness, and delamination fracture behavior [6, 8-12]. In contrast, for thermoplastic (PEEK, poly aryl-ether-etherketone) composites, experimental results show essentially no effect of moisture on longitudinal or transverse mechanical properties. Moisture-induced property degradation manifests a strong correlation with the degree sorbed moisture in the matrix. The rate of moisture sorption and the

solubility limits are governed by the matrix phase chemistry and by the fiber/matrix interface phase composition. Moisture sorption can be up to 10 times greater in thermoset composites than in thermoplastic composites. Moisture-related degradation is associated with chemisorption and reactivity characteristics of the permeating environment and matrix materials. Moreover, defects such as void, cracks, and other microstructural inhomogeneities associated with the fiber/matrix interface contribute to severity of moisture effects in resin matrix composites [7]. The deleterious effects of environments, such as moisture, on static (strength and stiffness) properties of PMCs have been well documented. However, research emphasizing the effects of moisture on fracture mechanisms and crack propagation behavior is inadequate. However, persistent demands for PMCs use in critical applications dictate that extensive characterization be performed regarding external environmental effects on fracture aspects.

Commensurate with the proliferation of PMCs in critical applications is the compelling need to understand and fully characterize static and fracture properties of composites in benign to eminently aggressive environments. In this investigation, the effects of moisture on delamination fracture toughness, crack growth, and fracture processes are examined for two composite systems, graphite/thermoset and graphite/thermoplastic laminates. The intent of this research is to assess moisture-induced fracture behavior in resin matrix composites.

2.0 Experimental Procedures

2.1 Materials and Specimen Preparation

2.1.1 Thermoset Material

The thermoset composite material used in this study was a continuous fiber reinforced graphite epoxy (Gr/Ep) fiber laminate, 934/T300. The curing temperature of a 934/T300 laminate is nominally 623 K (350° F). The laminate layup was unidirectional [0]₁₈ and the fiber volume fraction was 66 percent. The thickness of the graphite epoxy laminate was 2.4 mm. Both double cantilever beam (DCB) and laminate short bar (LSB) test coupons were fabricated from the laminate test panels using a diamond blade sectioning saw. For machined test specimens, very smooth edges were obtained with minimal cracking or edge fraying. The dimensions of the DCB specimen were: L = 90 mm, W = 20 mm, and thickness t = 2.3 mm. Laminate-short bar (LSB) specimens used to determine fracture toughness and crack propagation behavior were fabricated by a multiple step process. First, smaller size laminate coupons of dimensions, L = 28.6 mm x 19.05 mm x 2.4 mm, were machined from the stock laminate panel. Subsequently, adherends were cast onto the laminate coupons by way of a molding operation using a room-temperature cured epoxy resin system (Gougeon 105/206). Cohesively bonded epoxy adherends to the laminate coupons permitted the specimen size dimensions to be met as required ASTM 1304 testing procedures [13]. Following the molding operation, final dimensional sizing of the LSB specimens was attained by conventional machining. The LSB specimen is shown in Fig. 1. This specimen is a sandwich construction consisting of the composite laminate in the center with epoxy adherends on either side.

2.1.2 Thermoplastics Materials

A fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composite laminate (PEEK/IM6) was investigated also to determine the effects of sorbed moisture on fracture behavior. The laminate was fabricated from a unidirectional fiber prepreg tape that was 229 mm wide, 0.2 mm thick, with the fiber modulus being 280 GPa. The fiber volume fraction was 60 percent. Metal-laminates test panels were made by adhesively bonding aluminum alloy adherends to the PEEK/IM6 composite laminate using a heated hydraulic laminating press [11]. Consolidation was accomplished by heating the metal-laminate configuration at 666 K (393 C) for 8×10^2 s under 0.49 MPa (70 psi) pressure. A subsequent processing cycle consisted of elevating the pressure to 1.4 MPa (200 psi) and maintaining it for 1.8×10^3 s at 666 K to complete the consolidation. After consolidating, the metal/laminate configuration was cool slowly under pressure at approximately 1.4 MPa. The metal-laminate test panel is shown in Fig. 2 consisting of a unidirectional, [0]₂₄, composite laminate.

2.2 Moisture Absorption

Moisture was charged into the Gr/Ep and Gr/Tp laminates using a hygrothermal technique. Laminate coupons were submerged in a constant temperature water bath at 318, 333, 348 and 363 K. Moisture absorption characteristics exhibited Fickian diffusion in undamaged laminates. The moisture content and diffusion parameters were determined by gravimetric analysis methods. The diffusion coefficients are listed in Table I for graphite epoxy laminates.

Figure 1. The laminate short bar (LSB) test specimen.

Figure 2. The metal-laminate test panel is shown. LSB specimens were extracted from the test panel.

Diffusion Coefficient for Graphite Epoxy Laminate				
Temperature, K	318	333	348	363
D, [m ² -s] ⁻¹	2.87 x 10 ⁻¹³	5.66 x 10 ⁻¹³	1.43 x 10 ⁻¹²	3.63 x 10 ⁻¹²

Table 1. The diffusion coefficient for graphite epoxy composite materials.

Samples were weighed using an electro-microbalance with 0.01 mg resolution. Typical moisture absorption versus time profiles are shown in Fig. 3. In the early stages of moisture sorption, the weight gain (moisture content) by the laminates is linearly proportional to the square root of time. This suggests that Fickian diffusion behavior was obeyed, that is, $\partial C/\partial t = D(\partial^2 C/\partial x^2)$. Moisture absorption with time is given as, $M_t/M_\infty = 4/h(Dt/\pi)^{1/2}$ and the diffusion coefficient, D, is expressed as $D = (\pi h/4M_\infty)^{1/2} \cdot [M_2 - M_1/t_2 - t_1]^2$ [3,4,6]. The amount of moisture sorbed after time, t, is M_t . M_∞ is the equilibrium amount of sorbed moisture and h is the laminate thickness. It is of interest to note that the saturation moisture level of graphite epoxy laminates is considerable higher than the moisture saturation level of graphite thermoplastic laminates. However, it is found that the rate of diffusion of moisture in PEEK composites is greater than in 934-epoxy resin composites [9,10,12]. The activation energies for diffusion for PEEK and for 934-epoxy composites are, respectively, about 40 kJ/mol and 50 kJ/mol [12].

Figure 3. Moisture absorption versus root time profile of graphite epoxy and graphite thermoplastic composite laminates.

2.3 Testing Method

Fracture toughness, K_{Iv} , was determined using a modified chevron notch short bar specimen as describe by ASTM 1304. In this study, the K_{Iv} fracture toughness test specimen is designated as the laminate short bar (LSB) specimen. A desirable, useful feature of the chevron-notched short bar test is simplicity. In stark contrast to other fracture toughness test methods, measurement of the incremental crack length is not required. Since a sharp crack is initiated at the chevron notch tip, fatigue precracking is not necessary. Furthermore, once the compliance calibration is determined for a specified specimen geometry, the fracture toughness values can be obtained independent of test material [14,15]. Essentially, only the critical load is needed to determine the fracture toughness provided criteria for linear elastic fracture mechanics are satisfied. The short bar plane strain fracture toughness is determined by the following expression, $K_{Iv} = A\beta(P_{crit}/B^{3/2})$, where A is a constant that depends on specimen dimensions and the elastic modulus, E . The parameter A is given as $f(b, B, E)$, where b is the instantaneous crack front width, which widen with incremental crack advance, and, B , is the specimen width [14]. P_{crit} is the critical load and β is a dimensional correction factor for slightly misdimensioned specimens. Testing was performed at room temperature in air. Tests were perform in displacement control on a Fractometer II short bar test system. The grip opening displacement rate was 5.8×10^{-4} mm/s. Sharp crack initiation is achieved under the influence of a high stress field occurring at the chevron notch tip. The sharp crack grows to a critical length in a stable manner. When P_{crit} occurs at the critical crack length, the fracture toughness can be determined.

Double cantilever beam specimens (DCBs) were used to determine fracture energy results of graphite epoxy laminates. DCB tests were conducted at room temperature in room air. To facilitate testing, aluminum tabs were adhesively bonded to the cracked end of the DCB specimens. Testing was performed at a grip opening rate of 5.0×10^{-4} mm/s. Compared to the LSB test method, DCB testing was found to be exceeding more difficult. The difficulty was manifested by the arduous task of precisely measuring the crack length to obtained consistent fracture energy results.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 DCB Delamination Fracture

Fracture energy results for the graphite epoxy laminate are shown in Fig. 4. The fracture energy results were determined using the DCB test method. Fracture energies were observed for several moisture exposure conditions. For the hygrothermal conditions indicated in Fig. 4, an insignificant effect of moisture on fracture energy was observed. It was suspected that the fracture energy would be lower for more severe hygrothermal conditions. That a reduction in fracture surface energy was not observed for DCB tested graphite epoxy laminates under the most severe hygrothermal conditions may be related to the extrinsic contribution of fiber bridging. Fiber bridging in DCB

testing is known to increase the fracture energy of composite laminates subjected to hot wet conditions [16]. Furthermore, thin DCB specimens promote even higher fracture energy due to a

Figure 4. The fracture energy results are shown for various hydrothermal conditions.

significant enhancement in fiber bridging [17]. Presumably, without gross fiber bridging, a reduction in the fracture energy would be observed for moisture-saturated Gr/Ep laminates.

3.2 LSB Delamination Fracture

Graphite epoxy fracture toughness results determined using laminate short bar specimens (LSBs) are shown in Fig. 5. As indicated in Fig. 5, sorbed moisture degrades the delamination fracture toughness (DFT) in thermoset composite laminates. Significant degradation in delamination fracture toughness occurred with moisture sorption under severe hydrothermal conditions. The reduction in mode I delamination fracture toughness is approximately 60% following hydrothermal exposure of the graphite epoxy laminate for 1.3×10^7 s.

Figure 5. The effect of moisture sorption on delamination fracture toughness is exhibited for graphite epoxy composite laminates.

In Figs. 5 and 6, the variation of DFT with moisture exposure time is exhibited. Clearly, exposure to moisture sorption has a severely degrading effect on fracture behavior of graphite epoxy laminate, whereas, moisture absorption has virtually no effect on DFT for fiber reinforced graphite thermoplastic composites. It is evident in Figs. 6 and 7 that the influence of sorbed moisture on DFT for PEEK thermoplastic composites is nil. Several studies [11,18] have shown that the fracture toughness of graphite/PEEK thermoplastics is unaffected by moisture sorption. The striking difference in moisture-induced DFT between thermoset and thermoplastic composites is attributed partially to the fact that thermoset resin matrix composites absorb considerably more moisture than do thermoplastic resin matrix composites. As a consequence, plasticization by moisture of the matrix and interfacial regions is substantially more severe for thermoset matrix composites. Moisture

Figure 6. The effect of sorbed moisture is demonstrated for graphite thermplastic and graphite epoxy composite laminates after substantial exposure times.

Figure 7. The percent change in delamination fracture toughness is shown for thermoplastic and thermoset resins graphite fiber reinforced composites. No significant moisture effect is observed on the DFT of the thermoplastic composite.

saturation levels, M_{∞} , for graphite/PEEK and graphite/epoxy laminates are $\sim 0.2\%$ and $\sim 2\%$, respectively. Absorption of moisture in Gr/Ep laminates is about 10 times greater than in Gr/Tp laminates. Obviously, the maximum moisture content will depend on other factors such as fiber volume fraction, void content, residual stress resin composition, etc. Nonetheless, M_{∞} for thermoplastics laminates is considerably less. It has been suggested that plasticization of the matrix can lead to an increase in delamination fracture toughness [19,20]. That the DFT should increase was attributed to the enhancement in the moisture-induced crack tip plastic zone size. The contention was that the increase in plastic zone size due to plasticization enhances plastic energy dissipation at the crack tip, thus, effectively increasing the fracture toughness of the laminate. The decrease in the laminate fracture toughness observed in this study with matrix plasticization (softening) is in contrast to the previously published results [16,19,20]. This dichotomy can be rationalized by the realizing that there is a competing effect to ability of plasticization to dissipate crack tip strain energy, and, thus, enhance fracture toughness. This competing effect is the weakening of the bulk matrix and the fiber/matrix interface phase in the laminate due to matrix plasticization by sorbed moisture. Particularly, the contribution of fiber/matrix interfacial fracture to overall crack propagation and interfacial debonding in moisture-sorbed graphite epoxy laminates was rather extensive as note in this investigation. Morgan [21,22] and others [11,23,24] have reported several degrading effects of moisture on physical and mechanical properties of thermoset resins. Among these effects is that moisture lowers the tensile strength, elongation and modulus of epoxy. Also, sorbed moisture tended to enhance the susceptibility of the matrix to cavitation and plastic flow processes. Preferential cracking along the fiber/matrix interface is exhibited in Figs. 8 and 9 for a graphite epoxy laminates exposed to hygrothermal conditions. Examination of the crack tip region shows major cracking in the interfacial region and microcrack link up of the inter-matrix region with interfacial

cracking. In addition primary fracture along the interfacial region (interface phase) significant secondary cracking is observed. The secondary cracking is caused, presumably, by residual stresses in the matrix resin as a result of plasticization by moisture. The fracture characteristics of Fig. 8b are indicative of a weakened interface as the crack appears to meander from the top fiber to the lower one. Crack branching from the main interfacial crack is evident in Fig. 9. Macrofractography reveals such cracking branching as hackles [23,25] due to tensile stress relief in matrix-rich side of the main crack faces.

Figure 8. Fracture in the crack tip region is shown for graphite epoxy composites. (a) Fracture occurs along the fiber matrix interface. (b) Fracture is shown at the interfacial regions between to carbon fibers.

Figure 9. Near-crack tip fracture is shown in a graphite epoxy laminate material. Fracture has occurred in the moisture-plasticized matrix between the fibers. Microcracks and main crack link up are exhibited.

4.0 Summary and Conclusions

Moisture induced effects on delamination fracture were investigated. The extent of moisture absorption in graphite thermoplastic composite laminates is considerable less than that exhibited in graphite thermoset composite laminates. Irrespective of testing method, sorbed moisture had no significant effect on the delamination fracture of PEEK/IM6 laminate. However, moisture induced degradation was quite evident for the 934/T300 composite laminate. The delamination fracture toughness of the 934/T300 composite laminate was lowered by approximately 60 percent after sustained exposure to moisture. Plasticization of the bulk matrix and the interface phase by sorbed moisture influenced the reduction in fracture toughness. Moisture induced plasticization caused the resin softening and strength loss. Moreover, moisture tended to weaken resin in vicinity of the fiber/matrix interface. The degrading effect of moisture in epoxy composites was manifested by preferential cracking along the weakened fiber/matrix interface. Persistent fracture mechanisms appeared to be interfacial cracking and debonding and microcrack growth and coalescence in the plasticized matrix material.

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